

**A new species of the genus *Jordanoleiopus* Lepesme & Breuning, 1955
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Oman**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, Acanthocinini, taxonomy, new species, new record, Oman, Guinea.

Abstract: *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) annae* sp. n. is described from Oman. The new species is close to *J. (P.) monoxenoides* Breuning, 1972, *J. (P.) monoxenus* (Kolbe, 1893), *J. (P.) gabonicus* (Breuning, 1958b). *J. (P.) bifuscoplagiatus* Báguena & Breuning, 1958 is firstly recorded from Guinea.

Introduction

Jordanoleiopus Lepesme & Breuning, 1955 was traditionally regarded as a purely African genus (Tavakilian & Chevillotte, 2022) with more than 50 species of 3 subgenera distributed from South Africa to Somalia, where *J. (Polymitoleiopus) monoxenoides* Breuning, 1972 is known from. Recently one species of the genus was discovered in Asia (Oman) by Czechian and Ukrainian entomologists. It was published by Ambrus & Grosser (2012) as close to *J. (P.) monoxenus* (Kolbe, 1893) after determination by K. Adlbauer. Then a male was shown by Hoskovec et al. (2023) as *J. (P.) monoxenus* (Kolbe, 1893). In fact several series collected in Oman belong to a new species described below.

Material and method

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. Both photographs

were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

ML - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow),

OP - collection of O. Pak (Donetsk),

SM - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow),

YuS - collection of Yu. Skrylnyk (Kharkiv).

Taxonomy

Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) annae **sp. n.**

Figs 1-3, 5-18, Map 1

Jordanoleiopus sp. [close to *J. monoxenus*], Ambrus & Grosser, 2012: 452 - "Afrotropical Region; Palaearctic Region: Asia (Oman)".

Jordanoleiopus [?] *monoxenus*, Danilevsky, 2012: 720 - Oman, African Region.

Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) ? *monoxenus*, Danilevsky, 2020: 77, 293 - Asia: Oman, African Region.

Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) monoxenus, Hoskovec et al., 2023 - Oman and East Africa.

Description. Body black-brown; frons transverse, with dense deep punctation and indistinct pubescence; eyes rugosely faceted; genae about as wide as lower eye lobe; occiput smooth, convex, with very fine dense punctation, without central furrow; antennae very long, in males about 2 times longer than body, hardly reaching elytral apices by 5th joint, in females antennae a little shorter nearly reaching elytral apices by 5th joint; 3rd antennal joint is the longest, longer than 1st; in males it is much longer than 4th, in females 3rd joint a little longer than 4th; prothorax transverse, in males about 1.3-1.4 times wider than long, in females - about 1.1-1.2 times wider than long; anteriorly a little wider than posteriorly, with distinct basal constriction; lateral spines very sharp, bent backwards, situated behind thoracic middle; pronotum smooth, slightly convex, with pale lateral pubescence and central pale spot; elytra short, in males about 1.8-2.1 times longer than humeral width, in females - about 1.7-2 times; in males parallelsided, in females slightly diverging posteriorly; with fine dense scattered punctation, without erect setae;

each with a sutural dark stripe and 3 wide dark longitudinal stripes, repeatedly interrupted and partially reduced among light pubescence; dark transverse band situated behind elytral middle; legs moderately long, with pale pubescence, femora slightly clavate, in males more than in females; ventral body side with fine greyish recumbent pubescence; 5th abdominal sternite a little longer than 4th in males and in females; body length in males: 3.8-4.5 mm; body width: 1.2-1.5 mm; body length in females: 3.9-5.1 mm; body width: 1.4-1.9 mm.

Type material. Holotype, male, S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, 5.5 km N Rakhyut vill., near Ashqul vill., 16°47'45.07"N, 53°25'55.17"E, 833 m, 26.8.2019, Yu. Skrylnyk leg. - ML; 14 paratypes; 5 males, 3 females with same label - YuS; 1 male, 1 female with same label - OP; 2 females with same label - ML; 1 female, S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, 6 km N Rakhyut vill., Ashqul vill. env., 16°48'04"N, 53°26'01"E, 878 m, 23.VIII.2019, O. Pak leg. - OP; 1 female, S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, Dhalqut vill. env, 16°43'06"N, 53°15'32"E, 200 m, 24.VIII.2019, E. Ivanova leg. - OP.

Remark. The new species is very similar to several taxa distributed from Somalia to Gabon and Togo: *J. (P.) monoxenoides* Breuning, 1972 - Somalia; *J. (P.) monoxenus* (Kolbe, 1893) - Tanzania; *J. (P.) gabonicus* (Breuning, 1958b) - from Kongo to Gabon and Togo. All are closely related and have same type of elytral design; the validity of all names is not evident. The new species is strongly variable, and certain specimens represent many phorms known in African species.

Distribution. The new species is known from several localities of one area: type locality: S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, 5.5 km N Rakhyut vill., near Ashqul vill., 16°47'45.07"N, 53°25'55.17"E, 833 m; S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, 6 km N Rakhyut vill., Ashqul vill. env., 16°48'04"N, 53°26'01"E, 878 m; S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, Dhalqut vill. env, 16°43'06"N, 53°15'32"E, 200 m; localities published by Ambrus & Grosser from South Oman, Dhofar: Jabal al Qamar, 6 km W Dhalqut, 16°41'56"N, 53°11'29"E, 450 m; Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N, 53°11'40.56"E; Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N, 53°9'12.60"E; Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N, 53°16'27.26"E; Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N, 53°20'13.92"E; Jabal al Qamar, 15 km W Al Mughsayl,

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16°51'44.56"N, 53°43'18.38"E; Jabal Samhan, Tawi Atayr env., 17°5'16.94"N, 54°37'23.27"E.

Biology. According to Hoskovec et al. (2023) imagoes were connected with *Croton* sp. Most of our specimens were collected manually at night on twigs of *Jatropha dhofarica* Radcl.-Sm., but several beetles were attracted by light. Imago were collected on dead dry branches.

Etymology. The taxon is dedicated to Anna Volodymyrivna Lazebna the niece of Yuriy Skrylnyk.

Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) bifuscoplagiatus

Báguena & Breuning, 1958

Fig. 4

Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) bifuscoplagiatus Báguena & Breuning, 1958: 218 - "Fernando Poo" [île de Bioko]; 1958a: 1013, 1031 - "Ile de Fernando Poo"; 1963: 554 - "Ile Fernando Poo"; Sudre, J.-P. Roguet & Jiroux, 2021: 64 - "Guinée Equatoriale; Ghana; R.C.A., La Maboké; Cameroun, Menguémé".

Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) endroedyi Breuning, 1972: 232 - "Ghana: Ashanti region, Bobiri forest re."; Teocchi, Sudre & Jiroux, 2010: 19 - "République de Côte d'Ivoire".

The species is known from Equatorial Guinea; Cameroon; Central African Republic (CAR); Ghana. Now it is firstly recorded from Guinea.

Material. 2 males, West Africa, Guinea, Kindia, Tabuna River, 29.6.1982, 26.10.1983, S.V. Murzin leg. - SM.

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Figs 1-2. *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) annae* sp. n.: 1 - Holotype, male, S Oman, Dhofar Governorate, 5.5 km N Rakhyut vill., near Ashqul vill., 16°47'45.07"N, 53°25'55.17"E, 833 m, 26.8.2019, Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 2 - Paratype, female with the same label.

Fig. 3. *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) annae* sp. n.: male, S Oman, Dhofar: Jabal al Qamar, 6 km W Dhalqut, 16°41'56"N, 53°11'29"E, 450 m, 21-22.1. 2018, P. Kabátek leg. (photo by David Navrátil; determined and published by Hoskovec et al. (2023) as *J. (P.) monoxenus* (Kolbe, 1893)).

Fig. 4. *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) bifuscoplagiatus* Báguena & Breuning, 1958: male, West Africa, Guinea, Kindia, Tabuna River, 29.6.1982, S.V. Murzin leg.

Figs 5-12. *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) amae* sp. n., paratypes, South Oman, Dhofar Governorate, 5.5 km N Rakhyut vill., near Ashqul vill., 16°47'45.07"N, 53°25'55.17"E, 833 m, 26.8.2019, Yu. Skrylnyk leg.; 5-9 - males, 10-12 - females (photos by Yu.E. Skrylnyk).

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Fig. 13. Type locality of *J. (P.) annae* sp. n.

Fig. 14. Food plant *Jatropha dhofarica* Radcl.-Sm. (central tree).

Fig. 15. *J. dhofarica* with *Pristurus rupestris* Blanford, 1874 on the branch.

Figs 13-15 by Yu.E. Skrylnyk.

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Figs 16-18. *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) annae* sp. n. in nature (photos by Yu.E. Skrylnyk).

Map 1. Localities of *Jordanoleiopus (Polymitoleiopus) annae* sp. n. in Oman, Dhofar:

- 1 - 5.5 km N Rakhyut vill., near Ashqul vill., 16°47'45.07"N, 53°25'55.17"E, 833 m;
- 2 - 6 km N Rakhyut vill., Ashqul vill. env., 16°48'04"N, 53°26'01"E, 878 m;
- 3 - Jabal al Qamar, 15 km NW Rakhyut, 16°46'7.54"N, 53°20'13.92"E;
- 4 - Jabal al Qamar, 5 km NE Dhalqut, 16°43'22.48"N, 53°16'27.26"E;
- 5 - Dhalqut vill. env, 16°43'06"N, 53°15'32"E, 200 m;
- 6 - Jabal al Qamar, 6 km W Dhalqut, 16°41'56"N, 53°11'29"E, 450 m;
- 7 - Jabal al Qamar, 10 km W Dhalqut, 16°42'9.90"N, 53°11'40.56"E;
- 8 - Jabal al Qamar, 20 km NW Dhalqut, 16°42'39.31"N, 53°9'12.60"E;
- 9 - Jabal al Qamar, 15 km W Al Mughsayl, 16°51'44.56"N, 53°43'18.38"E;
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